

Study of detection algorithm of pedestrians by image analysis with a crossing request when gazing at a pedestrian crossing signal

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Abstract: Despite the advancement of information and transportation systems, inconvenient pedestrian crossing buttons remain common. In accordance with intelligent transportation systems (ITS), it is necessary to improve pedestrian crossing systems. Therefore, in this study, the proposed system adopts signal gaze, which is more natural compared to pressing a pedestrian crossing button, as a crossing request. A compact camera is inserted in a traffic light to view the other side of the crosswalk. The image data is analyzed in real time to identify all people who have a crossing request. An algorithm with three detectors using Haar-like feature quantities was developed and an evaluation experiment was conducted, considering three conditions: daytime, nighttime, and shade. The detection rate of crossing requests was 100% within 5 s. Although the detection rate was extremely high, there was a problem of incorrectly detecting non-humans. Therefore, in this research, we evaluated the system when detecting non-humans in order to determine the causes. As a result, it became clear that the detection rate changes rapidly depending on the waiting time for a traffic light and also when crossing the crosswalk; however, the system continues to detect the incorrectly detected background.

Keywords: Intelligent Transport System (ITS); Image analysis; Human detection

I. INTRODUCTION

For current traffic lights, pedestrians with a crossing request must push a button to switch the traffic signals. The installation of a pushbutton depends on the road environment and available budget. In certain cases, pushbuttons are inevitably installed in dangerous or inconvenient locations, particularly for vulnerable people such as small children, the elderly, and the disabled. Therefore, a means to install a new type of crossing system allowing such pedestrians with a crossing request to switch the traffic light is required.

Thus, to avoid having to move to the installed location of a pushbutton, attention has focused on stationary observations of pedestrians signaling for a crossing request (hereinafter referred to as the “stationary-gaze state”). In this research, we propose using the stationary-gaze state as a substitute for a pushbutton as a means of transmitting a crossing request. We evaluated an algorithm for recording a person on the opposite side of a crosswalk using a compact camera mounted inside the pedestrian signal lamp to detect a person with a crossing request based on image analysis using Haar-like features. There are

essentially two examination tasks required for detection algorithms.

The first is the accuracy of discrimination between a person with a crossing request and a person without a crossing request. The proposed algorithm was investigated to determine whether a person with a crossing request has not been detected or has been misjudged as a person without a crossing request. This algorithm is described in Section II.

The second is a problem of incorrectly detecting a background as a person. The areas where image analysis is performed are limited to locations where a person with a crossing request would normally appear. Furthermore, a range was set for the radius of the detection circle in which the person is correctly detected, and the detection of an object outside the set circle is not considered to be a person. With these considerations, we succeeded in drastically reducing the incorrect detection of non-human backgrounds. However, if a background without people in a detection circle with the same radius as a person is evaluated, an incorrect detection will occur. Measures to reduce such detections are also necessary. For this reason, it is necessary to investigate the characteristics of cases in

which a background without a person results in an error. This is described in Section III.

We first describe the proposed method, the experimental method, and results of the first task. Next, the experimental method and results of the second task are explained.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Proposed system

As shown in Fig. 1, a camera is installed into a pedestrian signal lamp, and pedestrians on the opposite side are recorded. We propose a new system in which pedestrians with a crossing request are recorded, and their stationary-gaze state is detected using image processing as a substitute for a pushbutton.

Fig. 1 Overview of the proposed system

B. Detection

OpenCV (ver 2.4.9) was used for the image analysis. OpenCV is a library of functions related to image recognition for C, C++, and Python.

Fig. 2 Difference in darkness and search window used for Haar-like features

Detection based on the number of Haar-like features can be used for human detection. Taking face detection as an example, detection using Haar-like feature values is a method for discriminating whether an object is a

face based on the difference in local brightness within the search window, as shown in Fig. 2. By calculating the difference in luminance between the two regions as the number of features, it is possible to capture the local edge and line components.

Face detection using the number of Haar-like features makes it difficult to detect a face that is not facing forward. Using this type of detection, a person requesting to cross the road and who is stationary and gazing toward the front of the signal lamp can be detected. On the other hand, a person with no crossing request is not detected because such a person generally does not stop and gaze toward the front of the signal lamp.

With face detection, when the target is a person whose face is partially hidden, such as a person wearing a mask, the detection rate in an environment in which the optimum luminance cannot be maintained, such as at night, is greatly reduced. This was demonstrated in [1]. In addition, it was also confirmed through a preliminary experiment that it is necessary to secure an image where the portion of the face exposed is 60 pixels or more to achieve reliable face detection. This is the size of a face image that can be acquired when capturing the image from 9 m away at a height of 3 m above the ground, which is the approximate height of a pedestrian traffic light; the face detection rate at a greater distance is lower. For this reason, to operate the system proposed in this research based on an actual crosswalk, when face detection cannot be achieved, it becomes necessary to detect persons with a crossing request by applying another detection method in combination with face detection.

Therefore, in this research, upper-body detection using the number of Haar-like features is used in addition to gaze detection. Detection of the upper body can be achieved even at distances normally affected by poor luminance, and when the features of the face are difficult to detect. In addition, detection of the upper-body parts is more ambiguous than the face and thus, a high detection rate is expected; however, with this algorithm, a person without a crossing request will be detected, e.g., someone who is simply walking in the image.

The face and upper body-detection rates were examined for a person pointing an umbrella, and it was determined that the detection rate of the upper body was significantly decreased. Similar to a mounted discriminator, as a standard feature, OpenCV has a detection function using its own discriminator with a cascade structure based on the collected images. Thus, it is possible to refine the detection target by using a

discriminator that gathers the images of a person with a crossing request, who cannot be detected through face or upper-body detection, as described above, and generate a correct image. Therefore, we created an umbrella detector to detect a person who is pointing an umbrella.

C. Proposed Algorithm

Fig. 3 Outline of determination algorithm

With the proposed system, face detection, upper body detection, and umbrella detection are used. When a person with a crossing request is continuously detected at the same position under the assumption that they are stationary and gazing, it is judged that the person has a crossing request.

Face detection is difficult to achieve for people without a crossing request, such as people who are standing sideways to the camera. On the other hand, for upper-body detection, a pedestrian without a crossing request facing in any direction will be erroneously detected. This also applies to umbrella detection. To prevent this, we propose the following algorithm using a quiescent state as a necessary condition.

- 1) Face detection is achieved in two consecutive frames at the same position.
- 2) Upper-body detection occurs at the same position for four consecutive frames.
- 3) Umbrella detection occurs at the same position for four consecutive frames.

When any one of 1) through 3) above is satisfied, a person with a crossing request is detected. The outline of an algorithm satisfying this requirement is shown in Fig. 3.

D. Evaluation Procedure

Two evaluations were conducted to confirm the practicality of the proposed algorithm. One was used to

confirm the judgment accuracy of the crossing request of the detected person. The other was used to confirm whether a person without a crossing request was incorrectly detected.

1) Evaluation 1: All subjects walked away from the camera to a point 8 to 9 m away, and then looked at the camera while at rest for 10 s. This procedure was repeated 20 times.

2) Evaluation 2: A subject walked sideways to the camera at 8 to 9 m away. This procedure was repeated 20 times.

E. Evaluation Environment

In anticipation of its practical application, a small web camera (1280*720 = 0.96 million pixels) was connected to a small PC (Intel Core i7-5557U CPU, Windows 7 OS) for image capturing. As described above, stable face detection was achieved unless the person was wearing a mask, hat, or other object, and as long as the size of the face was set to 60 to 70 pixels in diameter in the captured image, as described above. Therefore, we decided to carry out the experiment in the environment shown in Fig. 4. The height of the camera assumes the height of the pedestrian signal. We conducted experiments in this environment separately in shade, sunlight, and at night. Six men, 20 years of age, (among the subjects, one was wearing a mask, one was wearing a hat, and one was pointing an umbrella) were used as subjects.

Fig. 4. Evaluation environment

F. Evaluation Result

For the experiments, the image rate on a small PC was 1.2 fps, and 12 image frames could be taken in 10 s. Whether a crossing request occurred was determined in each frame by the proposed algorithm using the crossing request judgment rate. The equation for the crossing request judgment rate is (1).

Crossing request judgment rate

$$= \frac{\text{Number of successful judgments}}{\text{Number of trials (20)}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The results are shown in Fig. 5. The crossing request judgment rate is 100% for the fourth frame shown in Fig. 5(a), and the sixth frame in Figs. 5(b) and 5(c). It was also confirmed that a crossing request could be judged with high accuracy (average judgment rate of 95%) by the fourth frame under any conditions. It was found that the proposed algorithm can reliably judge a crossing request in approximately 3 to 5 s. For the subjects wearing a mask or hat, a sudden increase in the crossing request judgment rate was frequently seen in the fourth frame (Figs. 5(b) and 5(c)). This is because the crossing requests based on the upper-body and umbrella detection are detected at the same position for four consecutive frames. In the sunlight and at night, it was impossible to detect the face of a subject wearing a mask or a hat, and the crossing request was judged mainly based on the detection of the upper body or umbrella. From these experimental results, it can be stated that the problem regarding an undetected person with a crossing request was largely solved. Even if additional objects that cannot be detected are discovered, adding customized detectors should solve the problem. As with umbrella detectors, detectors can be created using OpenCV's ability to self-fabricate detectors through image learning. This is possible to create detectors if the detection targets must be expanded, as was the case when upper-body and umbrella detection were added to the face detection methods.

On the other hand, in Evaluation 2, no judgment regarding a crossing request occurred for a person without such a request. Therefore, it can be stated that the proposed algorithm does not incorrectly detect a person without a crossing request.

III. INCORRECT DETECTION

Because the proposed algorithm relies on machine learning for human detection, there is the potential for incorrect detections occurring against a silhouetted background, such as when a human is present. To reduce this issue, the proposed system limits the capture range to locations where people would normally be standing for crossing requests. Moreover, a range was set for the radius of the detection circle in which a person is correctly detected, and an object detected outside the set circle is not considered to be a person. Based on these measures, we succeeded in drastically reducing the incorrect detection of backgrounds without

a human present. However, if a detection circle having the same radius as a person is monitored for a background without people, an incorrect detection will occur, and measures will be required to reduce such detections. In addition, even if we improve the data learned through

(a) Shadow (brightness 900 lx)

(b) Sunny place (brightness 3500 lx)

(c) At night (brightness 1 lx)

Fig. 5 Change in judgment rate of crossing request.

machine learning, it cannot be categorically stated that no background exists that cannot be incorrectly detected. Therefore, it is necessary to develop an algorithm that recognizes an incorrectly detected background and excludes it from the judgment conditions.

It is necessary to investigate how people and a background actually differ when creating an algorithm to exclude incorrect detections of objects other than humans from the detection environment.

One difference between a person and the detected background is that the person will move slightly while waiting for the signal, whereas the background will remain stationary. Therefore, we predicted that the variance of the detected coordinates will be larger for the person than for the background. However, as a result of the verification experiment, it is virtually impossible to set a threshold value to distinguish people from the background because the dispersion value becomes large for both the people and the background. Some of the results of an investigation conducted using 300 frames taken on three subjects on an actual crosswalk are shown in Table 1. The table indicates the standard deviation of the detected coordinates and detection rate for the 300 frames of two incorrect background judgments (verification experiments I1 and I2), and the three subjects (S1, S2, and S3).

Table.1 Standard deviation of detected coordinates of the face region at noon

	X Coordinate	Y Coordinate	Detection Rate
S1	4.71	3.02	100%
S2	2.49	1.90	76%
S3	1.38	2.04	100%
I1	1.41	2.48	97%
I2	5.14	4.79	32%

Because there was no significant difference in variance of the detected coordinates, we focused on the detection rate in a subsequent experiment. In an actual crosswalk, a pedestrian will not be stationary when the light turns green, and thus the detection rate of the background becomes higher than that of the person. However, the detection rate over a long period of time such as 300 frames is low, and erroneous detections such as W2 in Table 1 may occur. Therefore, attention shifted to the variation in detection rate within a short period of time. For example, even when the detection rate is 30% for both people and the background, we believe that people will be detected only when waiting, whereas the background will be detected throughout the entire period. Therefore, if the detection rate is

calculated within a short time period (10 frames), it is predicted that a detectable difference will occur, as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Prediction of fluctuation in detection rate within a short time period.

A. Experimental Procedure

As for incorrect detection, we captured a crosswalk for 300 frames and investigated any objects that the proposed algorithm judged incorrectly, even if only once. We asked the subject to cross the crosswalk after looking at the camera for the first 150 frames. After having the subjects cross the crosswalk, we took an additional 150 frames, for a total of 300 frames. During this period, we examined the transition of the detection rate for every 10 frames.

B. Experimental Environment

We modeled an actual street crosswalk. The distance from the camera to the subject was 8.0 to 9.5 m, and the lateral width of the image capture range was 4.0 m. Fig. 7 shows the actual field angle used. The equipment used for image capture was the same as that described in Section II.

Fig. 7 View of experimental setup.

IV. RESULTS

Three background objects were detected for the face detection, and six background objects were detected for

the upper-body detection. The following figures show the data regarding human detection, as well as those with high and low detection rates for an entire background that generated an incorrect detection. Fig. 8 shows the face detection, and Fig. 9 shows the upper-body detection.

Fig. 8. Fluctuations in detection rate within a short time period (face detection).

Fig. 9. Fluctuations in detection rate within a short time period (upper-body detection).

With both face detection and upper-body detection, erroneous detection targets were detected throughout all 300 frames regardless of the difference in the detection rate. People were detected at a very high detection rate while gazing at a signal in front of the pedestrian crossing, and were not detected at all after 150 frames. For human detection, the overall detection rate was

approximately 40%, but the detection rate within a short time was much lower. In contrast, there was not much difference between the overall detection rate and the short detection rate regardless of the difference in elevation for the background of an incorrectly-detected target. It is considered that incorrectly-detected targets can be specified and eliminated by utilizing this feature.

V. DISCUSSION

In this research, we proposed substituting a pushbutton with a stationary-gaze state as a crossing request method. For this reason, we conducted an experiment to examine a decision algorithm to judge whether a pedestrian is in a stationary-gaze state based on image analysis using OpenCV. The results indicate that the proposed algorithm can accurately distinguish a person with a crossing request from a person without a crossing request. However, a background object captured by the camera may be incorrectly detected as a person.

When examining whether a difference in detection between a person and the background occurs, it was found that the detection rate rapidly fluctuates before and after the pedestrian crossing and thus, the difference in the detection rate shifts within a short time period. On the other hand, erroneously detected background targets are continuously detected regardless of the overall detection rate.

In the future, we will make use of these results to create algorithms for masking backgrounds that are incorrectly detected, and will verify the experiments. We will also conduct additional experiments under real-world conditions such as different environments and subjects.

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